

Period prevalence and point prevalence of sports-related injuries and illnesses in Swedish Paralympic athletes

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Abstract The purpose of this study was to describe among Paralympic athletes the 1-year retrospective period prevalence of severe sports-related injuries and illnesses (SRIIPS) and point prevalence of SRIIPS, and to examine possible differences in prevalence proportions of SRIIPS, between athletes with different demographics, and characteristics related to their behavior, impairment, pain and sport. A total of 104 Paralympic athletes responded to a questionnaire with questions about period prevalence of severe SRIIPS, point prevalence of SRIIPS, and athlete characteristics. Differences in prevalence proportions were analysed with chi-square statistics.

In summary, 31% (95% CI 23-40) reported a severe injury, 32% (95% CI 24-41) a current injury, 14% (95% CI 9-23) reported a severe illness and 14% (95% CI 8-22) a current illness. More severe injuries ($p < .05$) were reported by athletes that were 18-25 years, not using an assistive device, having pain during training, using analgesics, continuing training when injured and feeling guilt when missing exercise. Athletes that reported a previous severe injury, having pain in daily life and during training, using NSAID and being upset when unable to exercise, had higher point prevalence of injuries ($p < .05$). Being female, previous severe illness, using prescribed medications and feeling anxious/depressed were associated with more present illnesses ($p < .05$). Paralympic athletes, in particular of younger age, reported a fairly high prevalence of SRIIPS. Also, mental aspects as well as pain and use of medication seem to play a role in the occurrence of SRIIPS. This indicates that the existence of associated factors for SRIIPS is complex and calls for a broad biopsychosocial approach when developing preventive measures. Further large prospective studies are needed to identify risk factors and causations to provide stronger evidence for prevention.

Keywords Epidemiology, Athletic injuries, Sports for persons with disabilities, Sports Medicine

Introduction

Paralympic sport and Paralympic athletes' performances are steadily improving. As a result, athletes are exposed to more strenuous training and pressure to stay competitive. Increases in

training loads in combination with competitive elements may eventually lead to problems with sports-related injuries and illnesses (SRIIPS) that may compromise athletes' health. Data from the recent Summer and Winter Paralympic Games show that the incidence of both injuries and illnesses are higher compared with the Olympic Games (Derman et al. 2016 and 2017). Also, we have in recent qualitative study demonstrated that Paralympic athletes' perceptions of their experiences of sports-related injuries are complex and multifactorial, and in several ways differ from able-bodied athletes (Fagher et al. 2016a). Thus, there is a need to improve our knowledge of SRIIPS, to be able to identify and implement preventive measures (Fagher & Lexell 2014). The first step in the sequence of prevention is to describe and analyze data from comprehensive epidemiological studies. To improve our knowledge in this field, we have initiated the Sports-related Injuries and Illnesses in Paralympic Sport Study (SRIIPSS) (Fagher et al. 2016b). The overall objective is to prospectively estimate the burden of SRIIPS among Swedish Paralympic athletes using an eHealth application developed for Paralympic sport. At the start of this prospective study, the athletes completed a baseline questionnaire on existing and previous SRIIPS during the past year, as well as athlete demographics, behavior, impairment related and sports-related characteristics. This allowed us to analyse the prevalence of SRIIPS and associated factors, as an overall indicator of disease status.

Methods

Participants.

Participants were recruited through the Swedish Paralympic Program. 104 athletes (97%) with physical impairment (n=77), visual impairment (n=21) and intellectual impairment (n=6) completed the questionnaire. The median age of the athletes was 29 years and they trained on average 9 hours per week.

Data collection

The data were collected as described in a previous study protocol (Fagher et al. 2016b) and obtained from a questionnaire administrated in an eHealth application specifically developed and adapted to Paralympic athletes (Fagher et al. 2017) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. An eHealth application with survey design and technology adapted to Paralympic athletes with a broad range of impairments.

Statistics

Prevalence was assessed with descriptive statistics. To examine differences in SRIIPS among the athletes regarding their characteristics and behavior pair-wise comparisons were conducted using chi-square statistics for homogeneity ($p < .05$) with Cramer's V as measure of effect size. In cases where more than 20% of expected frequencies were less than five, Fisher's exact test was used.

Results

31% (95% CI 23-40) reported a severe injury and 32% (95% CI 24-41) a current injury, and 14% (95% CI 9-23) reported a severe illness and 14% (95% CI 8-22) a current illness. Significantly more severe traumatic injuries ($p < .05$) were reported by athletes that were 18-25 years, not using an assistive device, having pain during sport, using analgesics, continuing training injured and feeling guilt when missing exercise. Athletes that reported a previous severe injury, having pain in daily life and during sport, using NSAID and being upset when unable to exercise, had a higher prevalence of current injuries ($p < .05$). Being female, reporting previous severe illness, using prescribed medications and feeling anxious/depressed were associated with more present illnesses ($p < .05$). No significant differences in prevalence proportions of SRIIPS between different sports and impairments were present.

Conclusion and discussion

Paralympic athletes report a fairly high prevalence of both injuries and illnesses. In particular, young athletes reported a higher prevalence of traumatic incidents, indicating that they should be a target for future research. Also, pain, use of medications, mental and behavioral aspects seem to play important roles in the occurrence of SRIIPS. Accordingly, interplay between associated factors appears to be complex and calls for a broad biopsychosocial approach when developing preventive measures in Paralympic sport. Further large prospective studies following Paralympic athletes over time are needed to identify risk factors and causations to provide stronger evidence for prevention strategies.

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